

First steps in assessing paleoseismic activity along the eastern boundary of the Upper Rhine Graben

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Abstract: The Upper Rhine Graben is a large N-S structure inherited from the Oligo-Miocene extensional phase in Europe. It is now a moderately active area with steady seismicity (up to ca. M5) and strong historical events (M6.5+). To date, few studies have documented the paleoearthquake history of the structures that bound the graben, while the area encompasses critical facilities in a vulnerable region (dense population, agriculture, mining, geothermal facilities). Our project aims to fill this gap of knowledge in large and infrequent earthquakes, through a paleoseismological investigation of eastern side faults. Due to unfavourable conditions in terms of climate, low slip rates and high erosional/sedimentary rates, and human occupancy achieving this goal requires the use of a series of preliminary techniques to select appropriate trenching sites. We (will) use shallow and sub-surface geophysics (seismic reflection, electrical tomography, georadar), high-resolution LiDAR-derived DEM, shallow drilling and geological mapping. Here, we present the preliminary analysis of geophysical and geomorphological data that provide hints on potentially relevant places for future trenching (Karlsruhe, South Freiburg).

Key words: Paleoseismicity, Geomorphology, Shallow and Sub-surface geophysics, Central Europe.

INTRODUCTION

Characterizing seismic hazard at low probabilities of occurrence in moderately active areas requires information on the prehistoric earthquake recordings, beyond the duration of catalogues.

The Upper Rhine Graben (URG), and especially its southern section, has a significant network of potentially hazardous installations in a densely populated area and a vulnerable socio-economic environment (agriculture). Geological investigations are required to assess the safety of these facilities. Surprisingly, this region has rarely been investigated in terms of neotectonics and especially paleoseismicity: the most striking and successful studies were performed in the southernmost Basel region (Meghraoui et al. 2001) and along the western side of the URG (Strasbourg area: Lemeille et al., 1999; Mainz zone: Peters et al. 2005).

The primary objective of our project is to provide the first evaluation of paleoseismic activity of the fault(s) that bound the URG to the East. For this purpose, we are using complementary techniques to identify the best sites for trenching. The techniques include re-processing existing seismic lines, performing shallow geophysics, interpreting LiDAR data and geological maps, etc. Here are some of the preliminary results.

STRUCTURAL AND TECTONIC CONTEXT

Two European projects, EUCOR-URGENT (see International Journal of Earth Sciences Special Issue Volume 94, Issue 4, September 2005) and GeORG (<http://www.geopotenziale.org/>), provide geological framework, tectonic history and structure of the URG.

The URG is an inherited extensional mega-structure which formed, together with the Bresse (BG) and Limagne (LG) Grabens, the continental part of the Central European Cenozoic Rift System. Extension has stretched the crust over 5 km during the Oligo-Miocene times.

The Upper Rhine Graben provided accommodation space for deposition and preservation of Tertiary sediments (max. 5000 m in the northern part, around and north of Karlsruhe; 2500 m south of Freiburg) and is intensely sliced by post-Tertiary NNE-SSW faults. The internal parts of the URG include significant salt-bearing layers, giving rise to diapirs. Plio-Quaternary alluvial deposits are ~1000 m thick north of Karlsruhe (Mannheim), but only 250 m south of Freiburg. On the eastern side of the URG, alongside the Main Eastern Border Fault (also called Black Forest Fault in southern URG), Tertiary and Plio-Quaternary thickness maps suggest the pervasive activity of some "internal" structures, such as the Rhine River Fault. Nivière et al. (2008) proposed, based on morphological and borehole data, that this fault is active (<0.1 mm/a) and could generate M6.5+ earthquakes.

The current tectonic regime, with maximum horizontal stress striking NW-SE, imposes to the regional faults a prominent strike-slip regime, as shown by the focal mechanism (e.g. Edel et al., 2006). To date, large-scale regional GNSS network provides a maximum budget of horizontal deformation which cannot exceed 0.5 mm/y across the entire graben (Nocquet et al., 2012). The combined geodetic data (GNSS, InSAR and levelling) suggest local relative displacement in the order of 0.3 mm/y along the URG eastern border (Fuhrmann et al. 2015).

SELECTING THE RELEVANT TARGETS

To find out the right place(s) for trenches, we have to face a human-modified landscape in an active fluvial system: the Rhine River is the most powerful fluvial system of Central Europe. The sediment budget of this river changed drastically around the beginning of Quaternary when the URG started to drain the Alps (Preusser, 2008). During its most recent history (Late Pleistocene to Holocene), the valley floor was occupied by braided to meandering fluvial networks revealed in detail by high-resolution LiDAR data. Starting in the 19th century the Rhine River became progressively channelized to avoid flooding damage in this economically growing region. The combination of temperate climate, dense vegetation and low fault slip rates, however, makes localization of active faults a challenging task.

Our strategy is to develop a sound and robust pre-trenching analysis of the landscape and the graben infilling to select the appropriate site(s) where we can potentially expect the fault to cut surficial deposits. To do so, we first analyse several “industrial” seismic lines (on French and German sides) that potentially complement the European projects results. In addition, we use a very high resolution LiDAR dataset acquired by the Baden-Württemberg state, with a pixel resolution of 1 m and a vertical accuracy of 15 cm. Shallow geophysics (ground-penetrating radar (GPR), and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), were also carried out on top of the possible fault lines inferred from seismic lines and DEM analyses.

FIRST RESULTS

Thomas et al. (2016) presented preliminary results of investigations in the Freiburg area (Denzlingen) during the 6th PATA Days in Crestone. Several geophysical anomalies were inferred, although these sub-surface deformation features have no imprint in topography. Other targets were also defined and investigated.

Karlsruhe

Figure 2 illustrates the optimal resolution of the LiDAR: besides human-made features, the LiDAR-derived DEM clearly reveals fluvial landforms. On each side of a linear scarp (a-b), the fluvial pattern is different, suggesting a braided system to the East and a single-channel system to the West. The interesting point is that the fluvial landforms are obliquely cut by a 5km long and 0.5 to 2m high scarp, suggesting a tectonic origin (which needs to be validated later-on). Alongside this recent scarp, the LiDAR-derived DEM emphasizes hanging valleys between spectacular triangular facets along the Black Forest Fault. Even if this part of the morphology might be partly inherited from the main extensional episode, we suspect that topography could have been rejuvenated during the Quaternary.

Freiburg

In the Freiburg area, we acquired three “industrial” seismic lines, two of them imaging the Rhine River fault (Figure 3). Shot in the 1980’s, we have re-processed and re-analysed them in the framework of the Project. The fault is located in the Triassic to Tertiary layers but poor sub-surface resolution prevents any sound interpretation of its occurrence in the Plio-Quaternary layer. The LiDAR-derived DEM of the area suggests vertical and horizontal offsets of several features at the surface: on Figure 4, the large Staufen alluvial fan is disrupted where the fault zone (Rhine River Fault) has been geophysically inferred (Figure 3). There also it appears that some alluvial-fan related features (such as tiny creeks and related slopes) could be displaced in the left-lateral sense. During the first months of the study, our team performed many GPR and ERT profiles across the projection lines of seismic reflection-inferred faults and across the rare scarps, to test the possible occurrence of deformation features at the ground surface (see Figures 3 and 4). However, most of the potential deformation features in the alluvial plain are buried beneath shallow sediments and could be difficult to excavate.

Figure 1: Location of the study area in the Central-South part of the Upper Rhine Graben (URG). This paper focuses on two specific zones of the study area, namely Karlsruhe (see text and figure 2 for more details) and Freiburg (see text and figures 3 and 4). Zoom in around Freiburg shows a set of focal mechanisms, mostly normal and strike-slip small earthquakes.

The ERT profile across the Tunsel scarp (Figure 4) highlights an anomaly at the top of the slope that could match a fault signature. In the Freiburg area, the Tunsel scarp could be the best candidate for future trenching.

CONCLUSION & FURTHER STEPS

To improve our understanding of the fault geometry from depth to the surface, we plan to reprocess other “industrial” seismic lines that were consulted at the Baden-Württemberg geological survey. A new analysis of the Plio-Quaternary horizon in the GeORG database, in cooperation with the French geological survey (BRGM), will be done to check the occurrence of other shallow “internal” faults. In cooperation with geophysicists of the University of Strasbourg, we plan to carry out light-equipment high-resolution seismic profiles where surface geology (loess) is prone to transfer seismic waves and yield sub-surface geometry. These data will complement the electrical tomography profiles in order to precisely locate the fault at depth and its shallowest tip.

The LiDAR topography is a huge source of relevant data that requires analytical time before interpreting the landscape (in terms of fluvial dynamics and neotectonics). The Tunsel area (Figure 4) is a promising site because the fault line seems to be preserved at the surface, and is a potentially good place for trenching and estimating the horizontal and vertical components of slip rate. In this same area, we will analyse the large Staufen alluvial fan and its history, through morphological analysis, geometrical reconstruction, as well as dating of landforms and associated sediments.

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Figure 2: Nearby Karlsruhe hanging valleys along the Main Eastern Border Fault that bounds the URG to the East suggests recent activity. Several km inside the basin an outstanding 6 km long and 0.5 to 2 m high scarp (between ‘a’ and ‘b’) undercuts a Late Pleistocene valley fill (marked by white numbers and labels; figure adapted from Beckenbach, 2015). Inset shows field aspect in the northern part of the scarp.

- Map includes LiDAR topography (1m-pixel) and fault traces from various sources. Preliminary shallow prospecting geophysical results are also reported.
- Industrial seismic line was processed by CDP Consulting for IRSN

Figure 3: Example of “industrial” seismic line shot in the 1980’s, re-processed and re-analysed in the framework of the Project. This E-W section (84NBR105) intersects the Rhine River fault buried beneath the “recent” Rhine alluvium; this buried fault continues to the north and extends along the low relief escarpment in the Tunsel-Eschbach area (see figure 4). On the map, we indicate the “anomalies” inferred from deep (seismics) and shallow geophysics (ERT, GPR).

Figure 4: Detail of the Tunsel area, where the large Staufen alluvial fan is disrupted by the surface-breaking Tunsel portion of the Rhine River Fault. Several drainage features even seem to be left-laterally displaced. An ERT (electrical tomography) profile has been performed, showing an anomaly in its westernmost part (top of the slope). B.: outcrops of Jurassic limestones. DEM from 1m-pixel LiDAR data purchased to LGRB, Freiburg.